

Synthesis of 2,6-Dimethyl- Δ^7 -octen-4-one

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Starting from crotyl vinyl ether, the synthesis of the title compound has been achieved by making use of the Claisen rearrangement.

The acyclic monoterpene ketone, isolated from the oil derived from the flowers of *Tagetes glandulifera*¹, has been assigned the constitution (I) by Jones² on the basis of degradative studies. The proposed structure (I) for the naturally occurring ketone has been confirmed by the present synthesis.

Crotyl vinyl ether³ (II), obtained by mercuric acetate-catalysed vinyl trans-etherification of ethyl vinyl ether with crotyl alcohol, was subjected to the Claisen rearrangement⁴ to furnish 3-methyl-pent-4-en-1-al (III) in 88.8% yield. The aldehyde (III) on oxidation with silver oxide⁵ was converted to 3-methyl-pent-4-en-1-oic acid (IV) in 77.5% yield and the latter on treatment with thionyl chloride afforded the corresponding acid chloride (V) in 97.4% yield. The compound (V) on subjecting to the Grignard reaction with cadmium di-isobutyl furnished the title compound (I) in 42.9% yield.

The synthetic ketone (I) was characterised through m.p. of its semicarbazone derivative and the IR absorption spectrum, which showed peaks⁶ at 910, 1702, 1360, 1450 cm^{-1} .

1. Jones and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2530.
2. *Ibid.*, 1926, 2769.
3. Watanabe and Conlon, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 2828.
4. Burgstahler and Nordin, *ibid.*, 1961, 83, 198.
5. Clark *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, 6, 217.
6. Church *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1123.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Crotyl Vinyl Ether (II).—A solution of crotyl alcohol (26.0 g.) and mercuric acetate (5.5 g.) in freshly distilled ethyl vinyl ether (250 g.) was stirred under reflux in a nitrogen atmosphere for 10 hr. The contents were cooled in an ice-bath and stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. with sodium carbonate solution (10%, 130 ml). The upper layer was separated, dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and finally fractionated. The oily fraction boiling at 98–100° was collected and redistilled rapidly over sodium to furnish (II); yield 18.0 g. (50.8%), n_D^{25} 1.4230. IR absorption spectrum in CCl_4 showed peaks⁵ at 1190 and 960 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 73.20; H, 10.07. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}O$: C, 73.43; H, 10.27%).

3-Methyl-pent-4-en-1-al (III).—Crotyl vinyl ether (18.0 g.) was heated for 30 min. at 145–50° under nitrogen in a fully immersed, half-filled, sealed tube. Direct distillation provided 16.0 g. (88.8%) of the aldehyde (III) as a colorless liquid, b.p. 111–13°; n_D^{25} 1.4262. IR spectrum in CCl_4 showed peaks⁶ at 1720, 910, 2860, and 1370 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 73.20; H, 10.07. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}O$: C, 73.43; H, 10.27%).

The 2,4-DNP of (III) crystallised from dilute ethanol in light orange needles, m.p. 92°. (Found: N, 20.04. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{14}O_4N_4$: N, 20.14%).

3-Methyl-pent-4-en-1-oic Acid (IV).—The aldehyde (III) (6.9 g.) in ethanol (230 ml) was oxidised according to the procedure of Clark *et al.*⁵ with a solution of silver nitrate (12.4 g.) in water (130 ml) and NaOH solution (2.5%, 500 ml). Working up in the usual manner and subsequent distillation under vacuum furnished (IV) as a colorless oil, b.p. 92–93°/10 mm, yield 6.2 g. (77.5%); n_D^{25} 1.4275. IR spectrum in CCl_4 showed peaks⁷ at 910, 1700, and 2860 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 62.98; H, 8.98. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}O_2$: C, 63.13; H, 8.83%).

3-Methyl-pent-4-en-1-oyl Chloride (V).—A solution of the acid (IV) (6.2 g.) in thionyl chloride (7.5 g.) was heated under reflux till the evolution of HCl gas had ceased. It was then evaporated. Distillation of the residue provided the acid chloride (V); yield 7.0 g. (97.4%), b.p. 135–36°, n_D^{25} 1.4590. (Found: C, 54.04; H, 6.75; Cl, 26.50. Calc. for C_6H_9OCl : C, 54.34; H, 6.79; Cl, 26.80%).

2,6-Dimethyl- Δ^7 -octen-4-one (I).—A Grignard solution was made from isobutyl bromide (17.0 g.), magnesium (2.85 g.), and ether (60 ml). Finely powdered anhydrous cadmium chloride (9.84 g.) was added with stirring; the stirring was continued at 30° until the Gilman test was negative. Dry benzene (20 ml) was added and about 20 ml of this distilled to remove the ether. 3-Methyl-pent-4-en-1-oyl chloride (7.0 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml) was added dropwise with cooling, and the reaction completed by stirring at 80° for 40 min. After decomposition with ice-cold HCl (dil.), the benzene solution was distilled to furnish an oil; yield 3.5 g. (42.9%), b.p. 70°/8 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4300 (lit.⁸ reports n_D^{20} 1.4295). (Found: C, 77.53; H, 11.90. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{18}O$: C, 77.86; H, 11.76%).

*Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Drs. Wailer and Strauss, Oxford.

IR spectra were recorded on Beckmann I.R. 5 with sodium chloride optics, using 0.1 mm cells.

7. Cross, "Introduction to Practical Infrared Spectroscopy", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1960, pp. 57, 58, 63.

8. Simonson, "The Terpenes", Vol. I, Univ. Press, Cambridge, 1947, p. 101.

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 92° (lit⁹. reports m.p. 92.5°). (Found: N, 20.0. Calc. for C₁₁H₂₀ON₃: N, 19.89%). I.R. absorption spectra in carbon tetrachloride showed characteristic peaks⁶ for the synthetic ketone (I) at 910, 1702, 1450, and 1360^{cm}⁻¹.

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